

Hybrid Composite Application to the Boeing 767 Wing/Body Fairing

H. Nemoto

Aircraft Engineering Division, Fuji Heavy Industries, Ltd., 1-1-11 Yonon, Utsunomiya, Tochigi 320, Japan

ABSTRACT

A summary of advanced composite application to the Boeing Model 767 Wing/Body fairing is presented.

The 767 is the first commercial transport airplane to be applied advanced composite materials to the structure component from the early design stage.

Civil Transport Development Corporation/Fuji Heavy Industries of Japan participated in Advanced Composite Application Program to the 767 at Boeing and they have also designed the 767 Wing/Body fairing with advanced composite materials of Kevlar and graphite epoxy prepregs and are fabricating its production parts.

The advanced composite application to the 767 resulted in satisfactory weight saving and the joint program between CTDC/FHI and Boeing will be a successful international project.

INTRODUCTION

Oil price escalation has given designers a good chance to reassesses technology concept. The potential weight saving and resultant fuel reduction through the advanced composite materials are significant.

Fuji Heavy Industries has used composite materials, mainly fiberglass in epoxy matrix for the last twenty years and started the test programs for advanced composite application to a helicopter tail rotor blade and a rudder of a jet trainer in early 1970s. The composite rudder which was sponsored by the Japan Defense Agency had successfully more than 400 flight hours.

The Boeing Model 767 which was a medium range wide body commercial transport was made go-ahead in 1978 as a joint project between Boeing and CTDC of Japan of which FHI was a member and Aeritalia of Italy. Fig. 1 presents the development program of the 767 Wing/Body fairing. FHI project design engineers, stress and weight staffs, material engineers and manufacturing engineers went to Boeing, Seattle and joined the Boeing development team for the advanced composite application program and the preliminary design of the 767.

Fig. 1 767 Wing/Body Fairing Development Program

The 767 Wing/Body fairing consists of conventional aluminum built-up support structures, and Kevlar/graphite epoxy hybrid composite face sheets and Nomex honeycomb core sandwich panels. It is a aerodynamic fairing and also a storage area of the various equipments of the Environmental Control System (ECS), the Air Driven Pump (ADP), the Ram Air Turbine (RAT) and so on as shown in Fig. 2. Therefore, the fairing panels consists of access panels with hinges and latches and fixed panels attached to the support structures with fasteners. For the maintenance requirement, the ECS door of 110in. long x 50in. wide is made of one piece co-cured honeycomb sandwich panel of Kevlar/graphite epoxy face sheets and Nomex core and moreover, the Main Landing Gear door is one piece honeycomb sandwich panel of 120in. long x 90in. wide with the pre-cured core assembly as shown in Figs. 3 and 4.

Fig. 2 767 Wing/Body Fairing

Fig. 3 Main Landing Gear Door

Fig. 4 Core Assembly for Main Landing Gear Door

PANEL DESIGN

The 767 Wing/Body fairing was mainly designed under the following design requirement:

1. strength
2. stiffness
3. wing and fuselage deflection.

1.5 to 6 psi. of bursting and collapsing air pressure loads were given on the fairing panels by the wind tunnel tests. The waviness requirement was set for panel stiffness. It consists of 0.15in./100in. of the critical area in the wing leading edge and 0.5in./100in. of the non-critical area in the others. To prevent the introduction of high loads to the fairing panels by the deflection between the wing and the fuselage, the panels are attached to the support structure with plus or minus 0.1 in. radial floating nutplates and the support structures have single pin joints or swing link joints to be installed to the wing or the body as shown in Figs. 5 and 6.

The 767 fairing panel configuration started from the Model 737/747s with fiberglass face sheet and Nomex core honeycomb sandwich panel as a baseline. Meanwhile, it was expected that the use of the advanced composite materials would produce fairly weight saving. Therefore, trade study on the fairing honeycomb panels was done for various combination of the composite materials of Kevlar, graphite and fiberglass in epoxy matrix. Though Kevlar has very high tensile strength and high modulus, the compression strength of its woven fabric will decrease to 40 percent of the tension strength. Kevlar structures with graphite added could improve stiffness or compression strength. In the conclusion of the trade study, Kevlar/graphite cloth hybrid construction could obtain most weight saving of approximately 30 percent comparing with the baseline configuration of fiberglass as shown in Fig. 7. Finally, Kevlar/graphite cloth hybrid configuration has been selected for the 767 Wing/Body fairing panels.

Fig. 5 Typical Attachment of Fairing Panel to Support Structure

Fig. 6 Swing Link Joint

FACING MATERIAL	WING/BODY FAIRING PANEL WEIGHT (LBS)	SAVING WEIGHT	
		(LBS)	(%)
FIBERGLASS	880	0	0
KEVLAR	696	184	21
GRAPHITE CLOTH	656	224	25
GRAPHITE CLOTH + KEVLAR	619	261	30
GRAPHITE TAPE + KEVLAR	695	185	21
GRAPHITE CLOTH + FIBERGLASS	722	158	18

Fig. 7 Wing/Body Fairing Panel Weight Comparison

The self-adhesive prepregs are particularly desirable in the honeycomb sandwich, because core can be bonded to the face sheets without the additional adhesives and it results in weight and cost savings. At the beginning of the preliminary design graphite/epoxy prepreg was non adhesive resin system and the configuration was to put Kevlar prepreg against the core as adhesive and graphite prepreg on the outer surface. However, outer surface of the panels which is exposed to the airflow is co-cured with flame sprayed aluminum for effective antenna pattern, and it might result in galvanic corrosion between graphite and aluminum. At the long beam flexure test of the honeycomb sandwich panel, the strength values obtained were considered inadequate with the data variation. Two recommendations were made to improve part quality of the Wing/Body fairing test panels. These were,

1. to raise the resin content of the prepregs
2. to change the resin system on the graphite to the self-adhesive resin used on the Kevlar prepregs.

The additional tests were conducted at FHI and Boeing to determine the effects of the above changes. The test data indicated those changes would provide adequate mechanical properties. Then, the graphite face sheets have been moved against the core and Kevlar to the outer surface and minimum gage of the panel face sheet is 0.0135 in. with one ply each of Kevlar and graphite. To minimize galvanic corrosion problems at the edgeband fasteners of panels, it is standard design practice to terminate all graphite skin plies at the edge of the honeycomb core detail and not to allow it to extend through the edgeband area. The outer surface of the fairing panel has thicker Kevlar ply than the inner one for the impact resistance. Fig. 8 shows the final Kevlar/graphite hybrid honeycomb sandwich panel configuration with Nomex core and honeycomb beam construction is used for reinforcement of the cut-out of panels as shown in Fig. 9. Tedlar film is co-cured on the inner surface to provide a moisture barrier. The outer surface finish consists of a static conditioner, primer and polyurethane enamel.

Fig. 8 Hybrid Panel Configuration

Fig. 9 Honeycomb Beam Construction

PANEL FABRICATION

The lay-up molds for the fairing panels which are made of fiberglass material have been developed from the full scale Plaster Model. The molds of fiberglass material are easy to manufacture for complex contour as fairing panels and it is expected to be used over one hundred times of the cure cycle.

Kevlar/graphite hybrid honeycomb sandwich panels are cured in the autoclave in the 250 degrees F cure cycle as shown in Fig. 10. On the process of the production of the panels, there were several problems to be solved:

1. panel flexure strength was varied approximately 15 percent. One of the reason came from the bubble in fillet between core and face sheet during the autoclave cure. It was improved by the cure cycle change to vent vacuum pressure in the core,
2. the panel edgeband thickness is nominally 0.10 in. of 10 plies Kevlar prepregs, but some panels had 13 to 17 percent lower thickness after curing. The cause was high resin flow of the prepregs and the excessive bleeding of the resin,
3. the ramp angle of the honeycomb core is nominally 20 degrees, however, thicker core panels sometimes had core slip or crush under the autoclave air pressure of 45 psi. To improve this problem core stabilization methods were done as resin dipping, adhesive stabilization, splicing in sections of high density core, change of Kevlar ply tie-down system and core septums. Sharp radius contoured panels have pre-formed core in an oven,
4. Kevlar material is too tough to trim and drill. The router bit has been developed for trimming and drilling operation of the panels and now additional fiberglass plies which are added on the edgeband for easy trimming and drilling during composite application tests can be removed without excessive fuzz of Kevlar.

Fig. 10 Cure Cycle of Fairing Panel

QUALITY ASSURANCE

Visual inspection is the simplest inspection method and the most economical as a nondestructive inspection method. However, visual examination is not useful for detecting internal delaminations and voids of the Kevlar/graphite hybrid composite panel because of its greater opacity. Therefore, ultrasonic inspection was investigated to inspect areas for defects as FHI had the much experience of the method on the metal bonded parts like a helicopter rotor blade. It is concluded that high frequency ultrasonic inspection conducted by pulse echo method can be well applied to the thicker face sheets like the Main Landing Gear door and low frequency inspection method of the Sondicator is satisfactory for the thinner face sheets of general panels.

Process control coupons are fabricated with each autoclave cure load of production parts using the same materials and simultaneously cured with the parts. The specimens are verified to meet the mechanical requirement by the beam flexure and flatwise tension tests with each autoclave load.

Materials used during panel fabrication and fabricating process are verified according to the applicable specification.

CONCLUSION

The 767 Wing/Body fairing which consists of approximately 110 of Kevlar/graphite hybrid face sheet and Nomex honeycomb core sandwich panels could obtain a satisfactory weight reduction of 30 percent comparing with fiberglass face sheet honeycomb panels. This contributes to the good performance of the 767. The initial concerns of the materials and manufacturing process have been all solved. The 767 fairing panels are being produced well at FHI and supplied to Boeing to install on the 767.

The cost and quality of the advanced composite materials are now making it possible to apply the materials to not only military aircrafts but commercial transport airplanes and future major concerns on the advanced composite material are,

1. to apply them to primary structures of commercial aircrafts to obtain successful weight and cost savings and it will need to hurdle some barriers as increasing the strain to fracture of advanced composite materials,
2. to establish the preparation for manufacturing products more cost-effective and more reliable like from aluminum material to secondary structures.